

Effect of National Health Insurance Scheme on the Employees' Performance in the Federal Ministry of Works and Housing in Nigeria

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Abstract

A healthy workforce is paramount to the realization of organizational objectives therefore employers seek ways to ensure that their employees' are properly motivated. The National Health Insurance Scheme was introduced to reduce absenteeism from work as a result of health challenges resulting in employees' productivity. This study examined the effect National health insurance scheme on employees' performance in the Federal Ministry of Works and Housing. The study adopted survey research design, primary method of data collection through questionnaires. The data was presented in simple percentage with the aid of tables, mean model was used to test the Hypothesis. Findings from the study revealed that, there is a significant relationship between the National Health Insurance Scheme and employees' performance in the ministry of works and housing. The study recommends that the NHIS scheme should be given the necessary support for them to serve the employees' of diverse organization effectively and probably spread their reach to cover more employees as it has been noted that the scheme is one of the factors that boost employees' performance.

Keywords: Insurance, Health insurance scheme, Employee's performance

Introduction

Prepayment methods for health care financing have been adopted as the most certain strategy to ensure universal coverage for healthcare. Most countries in the developed world have a prepayment scheme for healthcare and have existed for a considerable period of time. The essence is to reduce the high burden of chronic illnesses, disabilities, and mortality on the employee thereby, increasing productivity. In the last decade, several African countries have embraced prepayment methods to finance health care services (Odeyemi & Nixon, 2013).

In Nigeria, the National Health Insurance Scheme (NHIS) was established in 2005 with the aim of 'securing universal coverage and access to adequate and affordable healthcare in order to improve the health status of Nigerians, especially for those participating in the various programmes/products of the Scheme' (NHIS, 2015). The scheme which works primarily in the formal-sector is paid for with funds created by pooling the contributions of employees and employers. Contributions to the program are 15% of the employee's basic salary, with the employee contributing 5% and employers contributing the remaining 10%(NHIS, 2015).

The objective of the scheme is to increase access to health care delivery by reducing out-of-pocket expenditure for employees at the point of use of service thus reducing absenteeism when health problems occur among workers in their productive years. The Global Business Council on HIV/AIDS (2002) reasoned that with increasing absenteeism organizations will experience loss of skills and declining morale which is likely to lower productivity.

On the other hand, many scholars have endeavored to examine employees satisfaction with service quality in many health insurance industry contexts (Gyasi & Azumah, 2009; Mehdi, 2007; Asubonteng, McCleary, & Swan, 1996; Rust, & Oliver, 1994; Gronroos, 1994; Rust & Zahorik, 1993), few have related it to the NHIS context in developing economies, like Nigeria, but, non in Federal Ministry of Works. Consequently, healthy employees are an asset to the organization because the success and continued existence of any organization are determined by employees' performance. Soeters (2006) asserted that human resource practices including compensation and benefits positively and significantly affect employees' performance. The essence of this study is to assess if this healthcare reform, and strategy aimed towards providing effective and efficient healthcare delivery for citizens has any effect on employees performance in the Federal Ministry of Works, Nigeria.

Objectives of the Study

To assess the effect of National Health Insurance Scheme on employees performance in Federal Ministry of Works, Nigeria

Statement of the Hypothesis H0:National Health Insurance Scheme has no significant effect on employee's performance in Federal Ministry of Works, Nigeria

Literature Review The Concept of Health Insurance

Health insurance in Nigeria is controlled by the Nigerian Health Insurance Scheme and it is designed to protect subscribers from paying the full amount of medical services when they fall ill or are injured. In order to ensure that every Nigerian has access to good health services the NHIS has developed various programmes to cover different segments of the society. These segments include the formal sector (which covers the public sector, organised private sector as well as students of tertiary institutions and voluntary participants), informal sector (i.e. rural communities and urban self-employed), vulnerable groups such as permanently disabled persons, prison inmates etc, as well as other groups such as Diaspora family and friends, unemployed etc. There is therefore the need for retirees to enrol into the different health schemes. This is because as people age, more and more find that their daily activities become limited by chronic health conditions that affect their physical or mental well-being.

Health insurance is a social security mechanism that guarantees the provision of needed health services to persons on the payment of some amount at regular intervals. It is designed to pay the costs associated with health care by paying the bills and therefore to protect people against the high cost of health care by making payment in advance of falling ill. The scheme therefore protects people from financial hardships occasioned by large or unexpected medical bills. It saves money on the short run and protects the poor from medical conditions that can lead to greater loss of money on the long run (Nigerian Tribune, 24, May, 2010). It involves pooling of resources from persons of different illness-risk profiles and the cost of the risk of illness among those who are ill and those who are healthy, are shared. It has three main characteristics- prepayment, resource pooling and cost-burden sharing. Pre-payments under the scheme are fixed either as a proportion of the pay-roll, or as flat rates contributed by the participants. This means that payment is not proportional to the risk of illness of individual beneficiaries.

Many advantages accrue from participation in social health insurance. According to Nielson (2009), they include: broadening the sources of health care financing; reducing the dependence and pressure on government budget; increasing the financial resources and ensuring stable source of revenue for healthcare; ensuring visible flow of funds to the sector; assisting in establishing patients' rights as customers; combines risk pooling with actual support by allocating services according to need and distributing financial burden according to ability to pay; solves equity and affordability problem in providing and financing health services; and, improves and harnesses private sector participation in the provision of health services.

Social health insurance schemes also enable experts to reasonably predict the healthcare cost of a large group. By lowering the personal costs of services, health insurance schemes induce individuals to seek health maintenance services more regularly than they otherwise would thereby preventing potentially serious illness.

Contributions and Scope of Coverage

Contributions are earnings-related. The employer pays 10 per cent while the employee pays 5 per cent, representing 15 per cent of the employee's basic salary. However, the employer may decide to pay the entire contribution. Furthermore, an employer, in accordance with the existing contractual agreement between employers and employees, may undertake extra contributions for additional cover to the benefit package. The contributions paid cover health care benefits for the employee, a spouse and four biological children below the age of 18 years. More dependents or a child above the age of 18 years would be covered on the payment of additional contributions from the principal beneficiary. Under this programme, a beneficiary is entitled to out-patient care, pharmaceutical care, diagnosis tests, maternity care for up to four (4) live births, preventive care, among several others. According to the records of the NHIS, over 6 million Nigerians in the public sector are currently accessing the programme. They are mostly workers in the Federal public service and those of two states Bauchi and Cross River (Nigerian Tribune, 6, September, 2010, P.17; The Guardian, 5, September, 2012).

Rights of Enrollees in the NHIS scheme

All participants in the scheme enjoy certain rights which are as follows: Right to register and access medical care listed in the benefit package; right to change provider after six months of the receipt of an identity card, if not satisfied; Right to access care in any NHIS accredited provider in the country on emergency; Right to know the names of the drugs given to the beneficiary; Right to request and know the total cost of drugs (10 per cent); Access to genuine and efficacious drugs; Right to identify the specialty of treating personnel, and Right to complain about poor services from health care providers.

Concept of Employee's Performance

Performance is associated with quantity of output, quality of output, timeliness of output, presence/ attendance on the job, efficiency of the work completed [and] effectiveness of work completed" (Mathis & Jackson 2009). Employee Performance is the successful completion of tasks by a selected individual or individuals, as set and measured by a supervisor or organization, to pre-defined acceptable standards while efficiently and effectively utilizing available resource within a changing environment. Aguinis (2009)

described that “the definition of performance does not include the results of an employee's behavior, but only the behaviors themselves. Performance is about behavior or what employees do, not about what employees produce or the outcomes of their work”. Perceived employee performance represents the general belief of the employee about his behavior and contributions in the success of organization. Employee performance may be taken in the perspective of three factors which makes it possible to perform better than others, determinants of performance may be such as “declarative knowledge”, “procedural knowledge” and “motivation” (McCloy, 1994). Carlson. (2006) proposed five human resource (HR) management practices that affect performance which are setting competitive compensation level, training and development, performance appraisal, recruitment package, and maintaining morale. Tessema and Soeters (2006) have carried out study on eight HR practices including recruitment and selection practices, placement practices, training, compensation, employee performance evaluation, promotion, grievance procedure and pension or social security in relation with the perceived performance of employees. The study concluded that these HR practices have positive and significant associations with employees' performance.

The effect of benefits on employee performance depends on the existing compensation and performance management package in the organization. Employees respond to the increase in pay and benefits with a positive and productive attitude. Several studies have indicated that employee benefits are related to organizational performance. SoonYew (2008) suggested that both mandatory and fringe benefits had significant and positive relationship with employee commitment and organizational performance. Fringe benefits had higher relationship when compared to mandatory benefits. This finding proposed that when employees received more fringe benefits, their commitment to the organization tend to be higher. Committed employees tend to be more productive and contribute to the organizational performance (Cascio, 2003). Benefits improve business profits, increase employee responsibility, result in equitable treatment of employees and enhance their quality of work life. Compensation and benefits have been identified as the glue that holds many employees in place in their organizations (Odunlade, 2012; Sahoo and Mishra, 2012) suggest that employee benefits can be a source of competitive advantage. Employee benefits motivate their important decision when it comes to job delivery and performance (Cascio, 2003). High employee performance followed by high monetary reward will make future high performance more likely (Odunlade, 2012). In a study conducted by Ekere, (2013) he reported that the monthly take home package for private health sector workers in Port Harcourt, Nigeria appears very poor, and the availability of benefits was outrageously low. A very high number of workers in this section, including health care professionals

earn less than an equivalent of a thousand United States Dollars monthly, which is insulting and not a survival income in the very expensive economic, in lieu of the city. Although jobs were challenging, providing learning opportunities, the stress level was high and majority of the employees were not too satisfied with their jobs. He also found that there appear to be a high turnover employment wise, in the city as most of the workers have been in employment for 5 years and below. Employee friendly benefits help employees to be committed to their organizations and also put in their best which leads to better organizational performance. In the health sector, patients are better off when attended to by satisfied and happy staff that are happy with their jobs. Money motivates behavior when it rewards people in relation to their performance and when it is perceived to be fair, equitable and providing rewards that the employee truly value (Bernadine 2007)

Empirical Literature 2.2.2 Health Insurance Scheme and Employees Performance

Zirra, Mambula and Anyatonwu (2019) examined the effect of fringe benefits on employee performance using Nasco Group in Jos as a study. The study adopted descriptive survey research design, while regression method of analysis was used in carrying out the empirical analysis. Findings from the study showed that health protection benefits have a positive and significant effect on employee performance in Nasco group. It showed that the more health protection benefits are provided for employees of Nasco group, the more they work hard at their jobs and their productivity increases. Based on these findings, the study recommends that there is the need for Nasco group to continue the provision of health protection benefits to its employees since it will help them create a sense of loyalty and encourage their productivity in the company.

Fubara (2019) explored the nexus between compensation and employee performance of banks operating in Port Harcourt. The study used incentives and rewards as independent variables measured by health insurance, retirement plans and performance bonuses. The study adopted a cross sectional survey design with purposively administered structured questionnaire while mean, standard deviation and Pearson product correlation coefficient were utilized as the analysis technique, aided by statistical package for social sciences. Results from the analysis showed that incentives and rewards relates positively and significantly with employee performance, as it has a significant effect on job satisfaction, employee productivity and employee efficiency. Therefore, it was recommended that compensation is a strategic tool management can leverage on to enhance employee performance and it should be positively utilized as a veritable tool to improve motivation to work better.

Uzobo and Ayinmoro (2019) investigated level of satisfaction and health effects of the national health insurance scheme (NHIS) among federal civil servants employed in Bayelsa State, Southern Nigeria. The study employed a cross-sectional survey with simple random sampling to recruit 337 federal employees living in the state while a purposively structured questionnaire was used to extract data which was analysed using analysis of variance (ANOVA), multiple linear regression, and chi-square test. Findings from study's analysis affirmed that malaria treatment ($\beta = 0.737, P < 0.05$), prescriptions of drugs ($\beta = 0.187, P < 0.05$) and vaccinations ($\beta = 0.422, P < 0.05$) were good predictors of satisfaction levels and self-rated health status enjoyed under the scheme. Study established that these satisfaction so enjoyed has a way of effecting positively on the job performances of federal staff in Bayelsa

Ukwandu and Onyema (2019) investigated the effects of the monetisation policy on employee performance in the Nigerian civil service. Monetisation was proxied by fringe benefits; free residential accommodation, medical insurance scheme, transport facilities. The study employed survey research design with a purposively administered structured questionnaire while extracted data were analysed with chi-square statistics and Pearson's product-moment correlation statistic. Findings from the study showed that the monetisation policy has helped to enhance employee payment packages as a statistically significant positive correlation was found between high monetised benefits and high employee performance. The study found that the Monetisation Policy has had positive effects on employee performance in the federal civil service in Imo State.

Ekwochi, Nwudugbo and Okoene (2018) investigated the effects of fringe benefits on employee job performance in united bank of Africa (UBA) Plc. The study deployed constructs for benefits as independent variables; medical insurance scheme, overtime pay and annual leave. The study adopted survey research method with reliance on both primary and secondary sources of data. Structured questionnaire was deployed to extract data using the five point likert system while hypotheses were tested using the chi-square distribution formula. Findings of the study established that there exist a significant positive relationship between medical insurance scheme benefits on performance of workers of United Bank of Africa Plc as workers and family were adequately covered hence workers commitment and loyalty.

Nwannebuife (2017) investigated the effect of employee motivation on organizational productivity using as case study; May & Baker Plc, Ota, Ogun State, Nigeria. This study adopted a descriptive and causal research design as well as the survey method with a well-

structured self-administered questionnaire deployed for data collection and analysed with SPSS using multiple regression analysis. Results from findings of tested hypotheses revealed that most of the respondents disagreed that the organization does a lot as regards health and wellbeing of the employees' health and safety seriously. This greatly affect job performance as workers feel exposed and inadequately catered for.

Gbadago, Amedome and Honyenuga (2017) investigated the effect of occupational health and safety measures on employee performance at the South Tongu District Hospital in Ghana. The study adopted both stratified and simple random sampling methods with purposively administered questionnaires alongside with observation while the study analysed data with SPSS. Findings of the study from analysis carried out established that there is a positive relationship between the occupational health and safety measures on employee performance measures of the organisation as staffers gives there whole commitment to work fully aware that the organisation has adequate provisions for numerous hazards such as safety hazards, mechanical hazards, biological hazards, ergonomic, physical hazards, and psychological hazards.

Kuranchie-Mensah and Amponsah-Tawiah (2016) investigated employee motivation and its effect on performance in Ghanaian Mining Companies. The study adopted exploratory research design in gathering data from four large-scale Gold mining companies while inferential statistics were used to test for the hypotheses. Findings from the study showed that provision for health insurance scheme has a significant effect on employee's job performance coupled with the risk associated with the mining industry, there is still effective health and safety policy in almost all the large-scale mining companies to avert possible occupational health hazards. The study established that the safety and health needs of staff should continue to be addressed, particularly those exposed to toxic substances and harmful chemicals as well as other factors identified as affecting performance of staff.

Zameer, Ali, Nisar and Amir (2014) investigated the effect of motivation on the employee's performance in beverage industry (Pepsi, Coke and Gorment) from five major cities of Pakistan. The study used monetary and non-monetary motivational construct as independent variables while employee's performance was the independent variable. The study classified medical and health scheme benefits under non-monetary motivational factors as encouragements. The study adopted survey research design of structured questionnaire of 5-point Likert scale. While regression analysis and correlation analysis was used to examine the connection between dependent and independent variables

measured. Findings from the study revealed that that non-monetary motivational factor is positively correlated with employee's performance in beverage industry with p value of 0.000 which is significant at 1%.

Theoretical Framework Principal Agent Theory Propounded by Jensen and Meckling 1976

An agency relationship can be presented as any employment relationship wherein one party (the principal) depends on another party (the agent) to undertake an action on behalf of the latter. The formal agency literature presents two different but related models. The first one focuses on pre-contractual and the second on post-contractual issues. There is also a positive branch within the theory, mainly concerning the design of appropriate intra-organizational control mechanisms and governance. Agency theory uses the contract to describe the relationships in which one party delegates work to another (Jensen and Meckling 1976). The focus of the theory is on determining the most efficient contract in an exchange relationship in order to govern it, given the characteristics of the parties involved, and considering the fact that the cost of obtaining information and environmental uncertainty in business relationships make it impossible for the principal to monitor the agent completely. It is important to realize that most agency models define efficiency from the principal's point of view. The main assumption is that the principal is the dominant party in the relationship. Hence, rather than maximizing the benefits for both the principal and the agent, the 'efficient' contract ensures the best possible outcome for the principal, given the constraints imposed by the situation (Bergen, Dutta, & Walker Jr, 1992).

Two Types of Agency Problems, when the principal forges a relationship with an agent, it faces two distinct problems. The first one pre-contractual problem—arises when the principal decides to offer an agent a contract. The major issue here is deciding on the strategy to find an agent who has the characteristics the principal seeks. The second problem emerges after the principal and the agent have forged the relationship. It is called a 'post-contractual problem'. The major issue here is to decide on the information strategy that the principal should employ to evaluate and reward the agent's performance to guarantee that he/she will be motivated to behave in a manner consistent with the principal's goals. Precontractual issues are often termed as 'hidden information' problems and post-contractual issues as 'hidden action' problems (Bergen, Dutta, & Walker Jr, 1992).

Methodology

The research design for the study is a survey. This study collected data from the staff of the Federal Ministry of Works thus making a survey effective in executing the research. The study established the assessment of employee's satisfaction in the life insurance transactions in the Federal ministry of works which was collected using questionnaires. The factors was tabulated in the questionnaires and expressed using relative frequencies.

The total population for this study is the entire staff of the Ministry of Works and Housing, which according to the department of Human Resources is 1307. Taro Yamane Formula was utilized to determine the sample size for the study.

Taro Yamane Formula

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + N(e)^2}$$

Where n=sample size

N=total population size 1 is constant e = the assume error margin or tolerable error which is taken as 5% (0.05)

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + N(e)^2} = \frac{1307}{1 + 1307(0.05)^2} = \frac{1307}{3.27} = \underline{\underline{400}}$$

Sample size = 400

Stratified Sampling Method

N

----- * S

P

N - Is the number of element in the stratum

P - Is the population of the study

S - Is the required sample size

Table 1

S/No	Department	Population	Sample Strata
1.	Highway planning and development	77	24
2.	Highway design and bridge	78	24
3.	Highway construction and rehabilitation	120	37
4.	Highway materials	90	28
5.	Geo technical and quality control	110	35
6.	Engineering department/service (ES)	260	80
7.	Planning research and statistic	58	17
8.	Human resources management	65	21
9.	Finance and accounts	32	9
10.	Public procurement	70	21
11.	Reform coordinator and service improvement	77	24
12.	Public private partnership	110	35
13.	Department of Legal Services	38	11
14.	Internal audit	24	7
15.	Press and public relation	31	9
16.	Anti-corruption and transparency	42	12
17.	Servicom department	25	7
	Total	1307	400

Data Presentation Analysis and Result Table 2 showing the number of questionnaires distributed and how many retrieved.

Questionnaires	Response Rate	Percentage (%)
Returned	326	82
Unreturned	74	18
Total	400	100

Source: Field Survey 2022

The above table shows that out of 400 questionnaires administered to the staff of the ministry, only 326 representing 82% were completed and returned, while 74 questionnaires representing 18% of the questionnaires were not returned. The 326 returned questionnaires were used for analysis.

At this juncture, the average mean score is used to test the data from the respondents. The decision criterion is to accept any question with a mean value of 3.00 otherwise reject.

Formula:

$$\bar{X} = \frac{\sum FX}{\sum F}$$

EF

Where:

X = Average Mean Score

∑F = summation

X = Total number of variables

Table3 Questions on National Health Insurance Scheme

S/N	Health Insurance Scheme	5 SA	4 A	3 U	2 D	1 SD	Mean (x)
1	I am happy that the scheme was introduced	(124) 620	(131) 524	(0) 00	(49) 98	(26) 26	3.84
2	The money deducted from my salary for the scheme is too much	(50) 280	(69) 276	(0) 0	(107) 214	(68) 68	2.74

3	NHIS provision for me and my household has made me more positioned to do my work in the office	(135) 675	(100) 400	(0) 0	(42) 84	(49) 49	3.70
4	I am no longer absent from work because of illness	(43) 215	(43) 172	(00) 00	(109) 218	(129) 129	2.26
5	I am no longer worried about the cost of healthcare, drugs and treatment	(111) 555	(130) 520	(00) 00	(48) 96	(38) 38	3.69

Source: Field Survey, 2022

KEY: (SA) = Strongly Agreed, (A) = Agreed, (U) = Undecided, (D) = Disagree, (SD) = Strongly Disagree.

Discussion of Findings

Table 3 shows the response of the Likert scale questions and their respective means. Question one 'I am happy that the scheme was introduced'. One hundred and twenty four (124) respondents strongly agreed, one hundred and thirty one (131) agreed, seventy three (0) were undecided; forty nine (49) disagreed while twenty six (26) strongly disagreed. However, the mean value is 3.84, this shows that most of the respondents are happy the NHIS scheme was introduced. Interestingly, 50 respondents strongly agree that, 'The money deducted from my salary for the scheme is too much' while 69 agreed, 0 was undecided, however 107 and 68 respondents disagreed and strongly disagreed respectively. Nevertheless, the mean value is 2.74, indicating that most of the respondents do not think that the amount of money deducted from their salary is too much.

Remarkably, 135 respondents strongly agreed, 68 agreed, 0 was undecided, 42 disagreed while 49 strongly disagreed that 'NHIS provision for me and my household has made me more positioned to do my work in the office'. The mean value is 3.70 meaning that most of the respondents agreed with the assertion that they are more willing to give their best on the job.

Unusually, the mean value to the question 'I am no longer absent from work because of illness' is 2.26 meaning that most of the respondents do not agree with the fact. 43 respondents strongly agreed, 43 agreed, 0 were undecided, 109 disagreed while 129

strongly disagreed. The response to this question seems a little contradicting to the fact that employees' are more driven to do their jobs this could be because most of the illness are severe or that they employees are yet to totally change their attitude.

Finally, 111 respondents strongly agreed, 130 agreed, 0 were undecided, 48 disagreed while 38 strongly disagreed that 'I am no longer worried about the cost of healthcare, drugs and treatment' with a mean value is 3.69 which shows that most of the respondents agree to this notion. If employees' are less worried about the cost of drugs, then they would focus more on the job.

Conclusion and Recommendations

The study concludes that the introduction of the National Health Insurance Scheme has significantly effected on employees' performance in the Federal Ministry of Works and Housing. The study also found employees are still absent from work due to ill health and this should be further investigated to know why absenteeism as a result of ill health occurs.

Given the above summation, the study recommends that the NHIS scheme should be given the necessary support for them to serve the employees' of diverse organization effectively and probably spread their reach to cover more employees as it has been noted that the scheme is one of the factors that boost employees' performance.

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